

Speculation on Special Relativity and Wave Behaviour for a Photon and Free Particle

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Historically, a photon and particle with rest mass were treated as separate entities after Young's interference experiment of the early 1800s. This separation was strengthened by Maxwell's discovery of a photon solution in his electromagnetic equations.

The questions we then ask are: Why are photons and particles with rest mass both included in special relativity and can a particle with rest mass have a wavelength and frequency even though it does not satisfy frequency = velocity* wavelength? We argue that the answer to these questions leads to the use of quantum mechanics, not only to describe the free particle with rest mass, but its bound state as well.

Photon Properties

It was known about 1812 that a photon could behave like a wave and followed:

$$v = \text{Frequency} * \text{wavelength} \quad ((1))$$

Furthermore, a photon has energy because it warms up a box of molecules and momentum, because it may strike a target. Thus:

$$\text{Energy (frequency)} \quad ((2))$$

In other words, high frequency (short wavelengths) were known to be linked with high energy even if the function relating energy and frequency is unknown.

Secondly, without any reference to quantum mechanics or special relativity, it is known experimentally that waves exhibit a Doppler effect and this also holds for light and may be verified for light coming from moving objects in space.

Thus, experimentally, it is known that frequency, wavelength and energy change for light when seen from a moving frame. This experimental fact already gives a link with a particle with rest mass because both its momentum and energy change when viewed from a frame moving at a constant $-v$.

Special Relativity from the Point of View of Particle with Rest Mass

It is possible to obtain the Lorentz transformation without any reference to a photon. In particular, one considers a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t . As seen from a moving frame, it will move with $v = x'/t'$ and will possibly have a new energy (i.e. $E(m_0, v)$) as well as a momentum related to the notion of it being able to strike a target. At this point, momentum and E are not defined mathematically and we assume x', t' , i.e. that space and time co-ordinates, must change because $x=0$, t does not yield $x/t=v$.

If one creates a 2x2 matrix to allow $x, t \rightarrow x', t'$, then one has:

$$\begin{pmatrix} A & vg(v) \\ B & g(v) \end{pmatrix} \quad ((3))$$

Here A and B are unknown. (One would probably guess that ((3)) should somehow be linked to unitary transformation and so A and B are not really two unknowns as we later show.)

((3)) leads to: $x'/t' = v$.

If one applies ((3)) to mocc, $p=0$, then: $E = g m_0$ and $p = gv m_0$ ($c=1$) ((4))

If one assumes that $E > m_0$, and wants the magnitude of the vector linked with ((3)) to be constant, one has:

$$(0, m_0) \text{ transpose } ((3)) \text{ transpose } \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} (0, m_0) = (0, m_0) \text{ transpose } \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} (0, m_0) \quad ((5))$$

Or $EE - pp = m_0 m_0$ ((6))

This can be shown to yield $A=g(v)$, $B=vg(v)$ and $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/bb}$ ((7))

Here b is a constant velocity which is unknown and serves as an upper bound to velocity, a concept not found in Newtonian mechanics.

At this point, there is no link to a photon. One may find a link in one manner by noting that Maxwell's electromagnetic equations transform under a Lorentz transformation, i.e. (A, phi) are 4-vectors where $B = \text{grad} \times A$ and $E = -d/dt \text{ partial } \phi - \text{grad} \cdot A \text{ partial}$.

We wish to find a link with a photon in a different manner. We begin with ((6)) and note that for $m_0=0$, the photon case, one has:

$$E = pc \quad ((8))$$

If $E = hbar f$ and wavelength = $hbar/p$, then ((8)) would be consistent with the classical wave result, but this might be a coincidence.

We note that one may have a photon bounce between two mirrors separated by its wavelength L. As seen in a moving frame, this length is now:

$$L \sqrt{1-vv/bb} \quad ((9))$$

Physically, the wavelength must sit again between the two mirrors and $E'=p'c$ as c is a constant independent of frames as shown by the solution of Maxwell's equations. Thus, using $v = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$, one has:

$$L' = L \sqrt{1-vv/bb} \quad \text{so} \quad f' = f / \sqrt{1-vv/bb} \quad ((10))$$

If one considers the transformation of E, p with $E=pc$ for the photon bouncing between the two mirrors in the lab frame using E as rest mass and $p=0$ on average, then: (using $(0,E)$ as the vector in the Lorentz transformation)

$$E' = E \gamma \quad p' = \gamma v E \quad p' = \gamma v E \quad ((11))$$

P' is the rest mass portion E momentum seen in the moving frame and not associated with L' in ((10))

$$\text{This leads to: } \hbar f = E \quad \text{and} \quad \text{wavelength} = \hbar/p \quad ((12))$$

Thus, the transformation (Lorentz) developed for a particle with rest mass does indeed seem to apply to the photon which is described as a wave.

Can One Apply Wave Properties to a Particle With Rest Mass?

At this point, one seems to have a particle with rest mass m_0 which has no wavelength and frequency suddenly becoming a photon if $m_0=0$. The problem with this scenario is that if $m_0 \rightarrow 0$, but still $m_0 > 0$, then $E = pc + m_0 c^2$ is almost $E=pc$ constant and it seems unlikely that there would be no wavelength and frequency, but all of a sudden one would exist if $m_0=0$.

A counter argument is that no wavelength or frequency appears in Newtonian mechanics. This could be accounted for if the wavelength were a tiny number which is less than the x error margins in usual classical physics. In other words, the wavelength effect would only appear for tiny lengths.

There are other issues, however, associated with assigning a wavelength and frequency to a particle with rest mass. We try to consider these.

- (a) A photon is always moving and so does not decelerate. This means that it has a constant p which may change suddenly in an interaction. A particle with rest mass, on the other hand, decelerates to $v=0$ at the endpoints of a bound state in Newtonian mechanics.
- (b) Special relativity is violated if one uses the argument of a particle bouncing between two mirrors in a rest frame, even though it is not violated for light.

To see this, consider a particle with E, p bouncing between two mirrors space \hbar/p apart. In the moving frame, this length is now:

$$\sqrt{1-vv/bb} \hbar/p \quad ((13))$$

Again, the particle energy E is like rest mass and p and $-p$ average to 0, so one Lorentz transforms the vector $(0,E)$ to obtain: $E' = \gamma E$. There is no $v = \text{frequency} * \text{wavelength}$ equation

now to allow for frequency' = frequency g because $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ for a particle with rest mass. Thus, the arguments used for the photon do not hold.

In other words, if one uses $(0, E)$ and transforms to $E' = \gamma E$ and then uses $E'^2 = p'^2 + m^2$, one does not get ((13)).

If a wavelength is a physical entity, then it should touch both mirrors in both frames. Thus, special relativity is violated which is a serious problem.

In the case of the photon, $(0, E)$ yields $E' = \gamma E$, but $E' = p'$ ($c=1$) means that $p' = \gamma E$ which matches $L' = L \sqrt{1 - v^2}$.

How does one deal with this problem? If one considers that a particle with rest mass can have a wavelength, then it no longer interacts in a Newtonian manner, i.e. it cannot have $v=0$ at bound state endpoints. Namely, it must follow (a) and interact like a photon such that a constant p changes to p_1 after an impulse hit. Then, to describe the scenario of a particle with rest mass having a wavelength between two mirrors and not being outside (the infinite potential case), one requires a superposition of particle waves, i.e. a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s. Thus, it is only an average wavelength which fits between two mirrors, not an actual wavelength as in the case of the photon, i.e. the photon is not a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s while the particle is represented by $\exp(ipave x)$. In this way, special relativity is not violated, but one cannot have a particle with a constant p accelerate in space as in Newtonian mechanics. This only happens on average, i.e.

$\langle KE + V(x) \rangle = E_n$ ((14)) where

$\langle KE \rangle = \frac{\sum p^2 |a(p)|^2}{\sum |a(p)|^2}$ ((15))

Thus, there are significant consequences to assigning a wavelength and frequency to a particle with rest mass.

Why Doesn't a Particle with Rest Mass Satisfy $v = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$?

Classically a wave should satisfy $v = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$, but a particle with rest mass does not if one uses frequency $\hbar = E$ and wavelength $= \hbar/p$. In other words, $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ is not $E = pc$.

We suggest this is not a major issue if one interprets a wave in this case (i.e. a probability wave) in a different manner. $E = pc$ involves $c = x/t$. In other words, c is taken to represent the actual motion of the photon in space and time. If on the other hand, one defines a resolution in time and space as $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$, then one has a second equation, with $c=1$ of:

$dt \text{ resolution} = dx \text{ resolution}$ ((16))

We compare this to the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$. Taking d of this equation yields:

$dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx$ or $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$ which holds for a photon.

It, however, also holds for a particle with rest mass m_0 . Thus, we take the so-called wave feature to be linked with resolution in time and space and the same formulas hold for a photon and particle with rest mass.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to examine why a Lorentz transformation may be derived for a particle with rest mass, but then be applied to a photon, which has no rest mass. We argue for a link between $E=pc$ (from $E^2 = p^2c^2 + m_0^2c^4$ for $m_0=0$) with $v=\text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$ by considering a photon wavelength separating two mirrors in a rest frame.

We suggest that if a photon has a frequency and wavelength and satisfies special relativity, a particle with rest mass should as well. This leads to difficulties because a photon interacts in a different manner from a particle, i.e. does decelerate. Furthermore, if one tries to have a particle wavelength between two mirrors, one violates special relativity. We argue that one may only have an average wavelength sit between two mirrors as in the case of an infinite well potential. We further note that a wave scenario applied to a particle with rest mass means that interactions are no longer at a point. In other words, one must use quantum mechanical rules.

We suggest that a consistent description of both a photon and a particle with rest mass follows from the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ using $dA=0 = -E dt + p dx$ so that $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$ in both cases.